

D4.3 Final report on the lessons learned from providing Support Services

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Abbreviations, Terms, and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
HE	Horizon Europe
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
IG	Interest Group
LTP	Long-term Preservation
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDA Corpus	The body of work created by RDA over time
RDA-KB	RDA Knowledge Base
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SRIA	The Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TAB	RDA Technical Advisory Board
TG	Task Group
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

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Table Legend

Throughout this report, tables are colour-coded with final status indicators, as below.

<p>Excluded/ Not Achievable This task or output will not be achieved or has been removed from scope.</p>	<p>Not Started Not started as planned, or still to be done. <i>Should be the exception.</i></p>	<p>Challenges Remaining challenges, if any.</p>	<p>Progress Implemented and/ or available</p>	<p>Lessons Lessons learned and recommendations</p>
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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a final evaluation of the RDA TIGER project' Output Services Work Package (WP4). It tracks progress towards the solutions and remedies identified in previous deliverables, and describes lessons learned throughout the development process. It offers descriptions and status updates on the implementation and continued improvement of the main output of WP4, the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB). The RDA-KB and WP4 aims to ensure the high quality, usefulness, maintenance, and sustainability of the WG outputs.

The deliverable also provides recommendations on how the RDA-KB can be usefully adopted by the RDA community; lessons learned during the process of development; as well as how support for RDA groups can be further improved in the future.

The report is structured in roughly three main parts: the first (current) section is an extended executive summary, including main outputs, synergies, and challenges. The second part (sections 1-3) provides more in-depth detail on the outputs created in WP4, as well as a final status update of how various priority areas identified by the project have been addressed. Finally, the third part includes lessons learned and recommendations for future work.

Synergies and Exploitation

The resources and assets that comprise the RDA-KB are already in use in other Horizon Europe (HE) -funded projects, and additional opportunities for reuse and continued development have been identified. The table below provides an overview of existing and potential synergies at the end of the project with the RDA-KB, including projects that have already adopted related resources and assets.

These co-creation and exploitation opportunities have several benefits, among others by improving the return on investment in code and infrastructure. Additionally, by incorporating a larger group of people and organizations in the enhancement and expansion of the open-source code repositories that support the RDA-KB, they provide greater sustainability. The sustainability pathways that this provides are currently being explored by the project.

Table 1. Co-development and Exploitation Opportunities

Project	Knowledge Base Component			
	Dashboard/ Discovery	Graph	Publisher	Annotator

OSTRails	Access to user views of demonstration guidance elements (already built as PoC).	Adds more refined handling of guidance for a generic KB, using FAIR guidance as a use case.	Use to edit, import, reference, or create new guidance elements Not critical, nice-to-have	Use to edit, import, reference, or create new guidance elements Not critical, nice-to-have
EOSC Data Commons	Same as OSTRails (guidance), but add aggregated FAIR assessment results for repositories. Will start on this shortly ,	Generalise and make applicable to any KB, including type registry, tools registry UIs, use for FAIR guidance.	Editing, adding, and deleting entries in the KB - mak truly configurable. Tools and type registry CRUD. Perform FAIR assessments - working on PoC	Refine and use annotator to conduct FAIR assessments of any web-based resource with a PID or a predictable package structure.
EOSC EDEN	Access to the registry of interlinked repositories, services, and attributes. Allows profiling and repository selection/ appraisal/ assessment.	Generalise and make applicable to any KB, including EDEN registry/ attribute/ service inventory	Add, edit, and manage repository, service, and attribute descriptions. Import (harvest) from sources via UI, export a repository description to a FAIRiCAT JSON-LD file.	Can potentially be used to annotate (publish) information on repositories, services, or attributes directly to the KB from the relevant web resource. Not critical.
FAIRwise proposal (if funded)	Transfer code to UL and GRNET.			

	Use for (1) guidance and implementation support (WP6), and for repository selection (WP3) as a minimum	Use for repository selection and for FAIR-related guidance.	Use for package composition (indicating files, metadata, and other sources - such as maDMPs - to be packaged for submission, and/ or for FAIR assessment	Further refinement to use for package composition and for FAIR assessment in multiple web-based contexts.
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Challenges

During the project, two main project execution challenges related to the dataset of the RDA-KB (referred to as the RDA Graph), emerged for WP4 that required additional effort, causing a delay in completion of releases of software, and required re-allocation of resources. This delayed the delivery of a production-ready dataset by approximately 6 months compared to the implementation plan.

Harmonisation and improvement of the RDA corpus

The RDA corpus consists of RDA Recommendations, Supporting Outputs, and Other Outputs¹ that grew organically over a period of 10 years. These were initially committed to the RDA website, and then increasingly (also) published on Zenodo, and other web-based deposits. This meant that the structure and content of web pages describing outputs and supplementary materials changed over time, often requiring WP4 to do manual data extraction, since automated methods could not always be used. The organic growth, and community-based nature of contributions to the RDA corpus, also meant that associated (meta)data needed to be harmonised and improved, to be used effectively as the database for the RDA-KB and contribute towards the goals of WP4.

This process of improving the RDA Corpus was initially anticipated to be done by crowdsourcing the RDA Community in this effort. However, crowdsourcing was found unfeasible given the time constraints facing RDA Groups and their members, who rely overwhelmingly on voluntary contributions.

Instead, this task was performed internally by DANS and required a considerable effort. This included effectively building the database from the bottom up, based mostly on RDA website data; harmonising and deduplicating data; as well as creating and curating associated vocabularies. The effort to create a credible database delayed the release of a beta version of the RDA-KB and the Graph Database by at least three months.

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/>

Development related to the RDA website

The delayed roll-out and quality assurance of the new RDA website, developed in the period between late 2022 to spring of 2024, also caused delays and other downstreams effects on the development of the RDA-KB. The RDA-KB is largely dependent on data from the RDA website for its associated database, the RDA Graph, as well as other dependencies relating to vocabulary and registry services under WP4. As described in deliverable D4.3², this had two notable impacts:

- a. Pages that were available in the original website did not resolve (for example case statements, group pages, member pages, etc.). These pages are often included as resource links in the RDA graph data. The situation improved over time after the change in developer, but alternative sources - pointing to an archived legacy website - must still be maintained.
- b. The engagement with the development team for the RDA website to implement vocabulary and registry services had to be postponed while they attended to the issues encountered with the roll-out. This engagement was resumed in June 2024, the new developer was contracted to provide API calls for synchronisation towards the end of 2024, and work on synchronisation could start in RDA TIGER at the end of Q1 2025).

² See section 2.4, “Challenges”

Outputs

The following is an overview and brief description of the support outputs produced by WP4 to date. All systems and tools Support materials are made available .

Table 2. Outputs overview

Category	Output	Description
Systems and Tool Solutions	RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB) ³	The RDA Knowledge Base is a suite of services in support of WGs and associated RDA activities: publication, annotation, discovery, and preservation. The components of the RDA-KB are outlined below. The Knowledge Base and its components are hosted on kb-rba.org .
	RDA Graph	The RDA Graph is a graph-like database containing a comprehensive catalogue of metadata for the RDA Corpus: including outputs, groups, contributors, and RDA (-related) vocabularies. RDA assets are continuously synced with the RDA website via an API.
	RDA Annotator	A browser extension and service of the RDA-KB that allows RDA users to annotate text-snippets from any web-based resource with descriptions and RDA-related metadata and vocabularies, which are linked to users via their ORCID IDs. Resulting annotations are saved in the RDA Graph, and are viewable through RDA Discovery.
	RDA Discovery	A web-interface through which users can access and search data from the RDA Graph, helping users search and discover resource. It features dashboard- and list-types views of resources, which can be filtered by various vocabularies. The webframe is highly configurable, and allows users to save and share search results.
	RDA Publisher	Assists RDA users with the publication of RDA resources (outputs, supplementary materials, or any other resource) to both Zenodo and the RDA Graph, including RDA controlled vocabularies. Advantages include ease of use, and more consistent use of associated vocabularies.

³ For further technical details about the components and services that make up the Knowledge Base, see the Knowledge Base Documentation at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737222>

	Helpdesk	The Helpdesk assists working groups and other RDA members to request assistance with tools, software, templates, or any other solution element
	Support Materials Drawer	Provides the users with guidelines, recommendations, design elements, and other support intended to support WGs in their activities. Allows the
Materials hosted under the Support Materials Drawer		
Policy and Procedures	Policy: Outputs (internal) ⁴	RDA will benefit from a policy in respect of output production and publication - dealing with aspects such as licensing and access, branding, ownership, attribution, and maintenance.
	Procedure: Workgroup Creation and Life Cycle (internal) ⁵	This exists to some degree, but must be reviewed in the light of additional support materials, guidelines, mechanisms, and tools. ⁶
	Procedure: Research Processes ⁷	Procedures for annotation and referencing of resources and publications in the course of the workgroup's activities.
	Procedure: Curation of RDA Collections (internal) ⁸	RDA collections in Zenodo [2],[3] need accession procedures that will ensure consistency of materials and resources in the collections.

⁴ Included in: [F.37.5.1.1 RDA Deposit Guidelines](#)

⁵ [3.1.2 Procedure: Working Group Creation and Life Cycle](#)

⁶ Clarity is needed from RDA on how this differs from Case Statements required from new groups. Needs to be differentiated clearly.

⁷ Integrated into Working Group Guidelines: [3.4.1 - Working Group Guidelines](#)

⁸ Included in: [F.37.5.1.1 RDA Deposit Guidelines](#)

	Procedure: Selection and Maintenance of Vocabulary (internal) ⁹	The process whereby RDA identifies vocabulary and how it is governed and maintained must be documented.
	Continuous improvement policy (internal) ¹⁰	Internal policies around helpdesk, service-level agreement (SLA), tracking issues, and access to guidance, policy and support documentation
	Privacy Statement ¹¹	The official privacy statement of the RDA-KB, for users of the service
Templates, Systems and Tools	Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies ¹²	RDA needs to use standard APIs and encodings for its own vocabularies. These need to extend to and allow the linking of external resources as intended in O1 and O3.
	Templates for Output Reports, Recommendations, Standards and Specifications ¹³	This document aims to provide an overview of existing and planned templates, including their current status and development.
	Minimum Metadata Schema ¹⁴	These have to be differentiated for different output and resource types, while satisfying repository and RDA requirements.

⁹ [3.1.6 - Procedure: Selection and Maintenance of Vocabulary](#)

¹⁰ [3.6.3. - Continuous improvement policy](#)

¹¹ [3.1.8 - RDA TIGER WP4 - Privacy Statement - V1.0](#)

¹² [3.2.1 - Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies](#)

¹³ [3.1.7 - Templates for Output Reports, Recommendations, Standards and Specifications](#)

¹⁴ [3.2.4 - Minimum Metadata Schema](#)

Knowledge Base technical documentation	Annotator Support Documentation ¹⁵	Describes the installation and use of the RDA Annotator, a browser extension mainly intended for RDA community members, which lets you annotate materials through a simple menu that captures and annotates any material you select on your browser.
	Knowledge Base documentation ¹⁶	Aims to provide documentation for the Knowledge Base and associated assets. It should serve as the starting point for learning about how the Knowledge Base is set up and managed, as well as a means to navigate related assets.
Group Guidance and Support	FAQs ¹⁷	Common questions relating the RDA-KB and its components
	Preferred Formats	Preferred Formats for Dissemination and Preservation. These are needed to maximise utility for the community and to ensure long-term preservation.
	Publication of outputs ¹⁹	Guidance on how and where to publish WG outputs. Including advice on vocabularies, sustainability, depositing to Zenodo, and making outputs accessible
	Working group guidelines ²⁰	Guidelines around WG procedures, lifecycle, membership, maximising working group outcomes, including guidance on making outputs FAIR
Additional Resources	Standards	Development Recommendations from HSBooster: Recommendations from HSBooster for RDA on how WG outputs can contribute to standards development

¹⁵ Included in: [3.3.7 - RDA Annotator Guidelines](#)

¹⁶ Saldner, S., Hugo, W., Tobias, L., Polimeno, A., & Indarto, E. (2025). The RDA Knowledge Base: Documentation on the Knowledge Base and related assets (1.1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737222>

¹⁷ [3.5.8 - FAQs](#)

¹⁸ [3.3.7 - RDA Annotator Guidelines](#)

¹⁹ [3.1.4 - Publication of Outputs](#)

²⁰ [3.4.1 - Working Group Guidelines](#)

	Landscape analyses	Results from landscape analyses carried out in D3.5 ²¹ , including mappings of e.g. WG Resources, Horizon Europe projects, and regional and national resources
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²¹ Grau, N., Lehtsalu, L., Saldner, S. (2025). RDA TIGER D3.5: Final report on engagement and landscape monitoring, lessons learned. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877303>

1. Introduction

Research Data Alliance (RDA) Working Groups (WGs) are designed to address specific research data-related issues in a relatively short amount of time. These WGs are created and composed by RDA community members, and rely on their voluntary contributions from the community to achieve their objectives. Although this strategy has been successful, issues and areas for improvements were identified by the RDA TIGER to better support WGs in their work. An overview of issues and identified solutions that pertain to WP4 can be found in section 3. An area of improvement relevant to most RDA WG's is that since their work depends on the voluntary contributions of its members, time and effort is at a premium. The RDA TIGER project addresses these issues by providing WGs assistance with planning, engagement, communication, facilitation, and finalisation services.²²

The RDA TIGER project has established a suite of concrete services to support RDA WGs. Work Package (WP) 4: 'Output Services', has developed the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB),²³ as one of these services. The RDA-KB is a suite of applications and services that support the publication of RDA outputs, supplementary materials, and guidance materials, as well as cataloguing detailed metadata pertaining to these publications, both for RDA WGs, and the wider RDA community. Its objectives are to ensure the high quality, usefulness, maintenance, and sustainability of the WG outputs.

Figure 1. RDA TIGER Services

²² Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions (RDA-TIGER), Project Proposal. See the project summary on CORDIS for additional details: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094406/reporting>

²³ The Knowledge Base was previously referred to as the Maintenance Platform (RDA-MP). See annex A for an overview and motivation of naming scheme changes for the Knowledge Base and its components.

This deliverable is the final report of WP4. It describes the progress made in the final period of the project, and can be considered a continuation of previous WP4 deliverables: D4.1: Description of Output Support Services and Maintenance Platform,²⁴ and D4.2: Performance report on the Output Support Services,²⁵ and is therefore similar in structure. Specifically, D4.1 provided an overview of the issues, design considerations, requirements, and expectations of WP4, while D4.2 assessed the progress made towards implementation of the work plan outlined in D4.1 at the half-way point of the project. This deliverable provides a final update on progress made towards the issues tracked in previous deliverables in section 3. Before this, section 2 provides a summary report of the main outcomes of WP4. Finally, section 4 provides an overview of lessons learned throughout the process, including recommendations for future development.

2. Summary report

2.1. Objectives of Work Package 4

The objectives of the Outputs Service (WP4) are to ensure the high quality, usefulness, maintenance, and sustainability of the outputs of RDA WGs. It achieves this by producing guidance and assisting WGs in defining the scope of their recommendations, identifying the user community, following best-practices and standards, as well as providing instructions and recommendations to meet maintenance and sustainability requirements. WP4 provides expertise in the form of guidelines, recommendations, design considerations, and specifications, and also maintains an inventory of related policies, requirements, and specifications to aid WGs in their work. In broad terms, WP4 has two focus areas:

1. Ensuring that RDA outputs (recommendations, support materials, and related outputs) are properly curated and preserved, and that they are adequately tagged and characterised to improve their future findability and reuse; and
2. Providing mechanisms for describing and persisting the effort that goes into landscape assessments and desk research, especially during working group activities, effectively also turning these efforts into reusable and easily findable digital resources.

Addressing these requirements is the **RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB)**,²⁶ a suite of web-based applications and services developed by DANS in WP4. The RDA-KB provides access to the guidance, specifications, and other RDA-related resources described above, and also provides technical tools that assist WGs with the publication and cataloguing of RDA outputs and supplementary materials.

²⁴ Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2023). RDA TIGER D4.1 – Description of Output Support Services and Maintenance Platform (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096631>

²⁵ Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2024). RDA TIGER D4.2 – Performance report on the Output Support Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

²⁶ The Knowledge Base was previously referred to as the Maintenance Platform (RDA-MP). See annex A for an overview and motivation of naming scheme changes for the Knowledge Base and its components.

The Knowledge Base suite of applications and infrastructure described above, comprising the following 4 main service components:

- **The RDA Discovery** application provides a means to search for and access any and all RDA-related resources in the RDA Graph, and provides dashboard-like overviews of available resources (see Dashboard and Search tabs on at the [RDA-KB Website](#)²⁷).
- **The RDA Graph**, a graph-like database containing all RDA-related outputs and web-based materials that could be catalogued to date - including all resources formally published in Zenodo and the RDA websites (legacy and current). The contents of the Graph can be browsed using the above-mentioned Discovery application.
- **The RDA Publisher** application assists with the publication of RDA resources (outputs, supplementary materials, or any other resource) to both Zenodo and the RDA Graph. The approach has several advantages, including the ability to accommodate more than one metadata schema that may depend on the type of content, and to link to any number of LOD-type vocabularies and registries to better contextualise the resources. The Publisher can be accessed under the [Publisher tab of the KB Website](#).²⁸
- **The RDA Annotator** application is a browser plugin that can be invoked to create annotations for web resources, linking them via free-text and vocabulary-based annotations to the RDA Graph. See the [Annotator tab of the KB website](#).²⁹

Figure 2: RDA Applications in the RDA Knowledge Base suite, and its relation to Zenodo or other FAIR repository

²⁷ <https://kb-rda.org/>

²⁸ <https://kb-rda.org/publisher>

²⁹ <https://kb-rda.org/annotator>

As an unspoken but necessary outcome, one could state that the WP aims to make RDA outputs and associated resources FAIR.

2.2. RDA Knowledge Base

All components of the RDA-KB are available via the RDA-KB website, kb-rda.org. The website uses the DANS Frontend Framework.³⁰ The website and all components of the RDA-KB are open source,³¹ and are hosted independently of the RDA website, rd-alliance.org. This framework allows kb-rda.org to be customised and integrated with other web-applications and services, without making fundamental changes to the Wordpress-based rd-alliance.org website. If desired, kb-rda.org is embeddable on the RDA website, or any other website that supports this. Rather than using the Wordpress-based authentication method used by the RDA website, authentication of RDA-KB users³² is done via individual ORCID accounts, which are linked to a Keycloak implementation as middleware to manage identities and tokens associated with an account. The advantages of using this approach is that ORCID accounts can be linked to e.g. a Zenodo account or other services that link to ORCID.

In addition to the service components described above, the website also hosts the **Support Materials Drawer**, and **Helpdesk**. These can be found by clicking the “Support” and “Help” buttons in the lower-right corner of kb-rda.org. The Support Materials Drawer provides the guidelines, recommendations, design elements, and other support described above. The Helpdesk allows users to submit tickets for support, suggested improvements, or error reports relating to the RDA-KB. See section 2.2.1.2 for more information.

In the following sections, the features of the four main components of the RDA-KB are described in brief. For additional introductory information about the Knowledge Base, see Getting to Know the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Knowledge Base.³³ For additional technical details, see the official documentation for the Knowledge Base.³⁴ Finally, for user guidelines and information, refer to the aforementioned Support Materials Drawer.

2.2.1. RDA Graph

The RDA-KB now features a complete catalogue of RDA outputs and supporting materials, as well as the bibliographic data about associated authors, working/interest groups, and institutions, among others. The data is continuously synchronised via an API connection with the RDA website, which was developed in collaboration with RDA and their web developer, Maraméo. Considerable effort went into

³⁰ <https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/dans-frontend-framework>

³¹ For additional technical details, see Annex A of D4.2: Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2024). RDA TIGER D4.2 – Performance report on the Output Support Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

³² Authentication is used with the RDA Publisher, and RDA Annotator. See their respective sections below for details.

³³ Sharma, C. J. M., Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2025). Getting to Know the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Knowledge Base (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882751>

³⁴ Knowledge Base documentation available at DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737222>

consolidating, disambiguating, and deduplicating these records, which had been created organically over time. The resulting dataset is referred to as the RDA Graph.

The RDA Graph features associated RDA (associated) vocabularies, many of which were purpose-built by WP4.³⁵ These include RDA-specific vocabularies on e.g. RDA Pathways, group status, and membership roles; RDM-related vocabularies on e.g. licenses, domains/disciplines, and principles; as well as vocabularies created by RDA WGs and other organisations, such as The Global Open Research Commons (GORC) vocabulary.³⁶

Resources entered into the RDA Graph are linked to the above-mentioned vocabularies as well as to each other. This greatly improves the findability, harmonisation, and usefulness of these resources. Landscape monitoring provides a good use case for these features, as they make it easier to identify resources by e.g. topic, discipline, or associated contributors. Results from landscape analyses can also be integrated into the RDA Graph, further enriching the data, and making their findings available to other RDA users.

2.2.2. RDA Discovery

2.2.2.1. Search and discovery functions

RDA Discovery is a web-interface through which users can access and search data from the RDA Graph.³⁷ It features dashboard- and list-types views of resources, which can be filtered by various vocabularies such as topic, WG, or year, as well as free-text queries. The Dashboard interface is highly configurable and interactive, and can represent finding using e.g. geographical, chronological, or charts like representations. Dashboard views can also be saved and shared with other users, without requiring a user account. The List view provides a detailed view of the same results that are displayed in the Dashboard view, with all associated metadata, including abstract, URLs, and associated authors and WG.

RDA Discovery allows users to easily search and access the entire RDA corpus, to identify items of interest, and to associate them with various RDA (-related) vocabularies. These features make it easier for users to carry out a landscape analysis of RDA-related outputs, assets, groups, and more. The search results and dashboard/list views can easily be shared with other users (e.g. working in the same WG), to facilitate collaboration. The web-frame that underlies the RDA Discovery is highly configurable, and can on request, potentially be customised by RDA WGs to demonstrate the results of their landscape analysis.³⁸

³⁵ Hugo, W., Polimeno, A., Saldner, S., Laurens, T. (2025). RDA Knowledge Base: Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies [Data set] Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17771724>; also on kb-rda.org

³⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/outputs/ (accessed 2025.11.30)

³⁷ Accessible via: rda-kb.org

³⁸ For additional technical information about RDA Discovery, and other components of the Knowledge Base, see the associated documentation at DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737222>

Figure 3: Dashboard view of the RDA Discovery Application

2.2.2.2. Support documentation and helpdesk

The RDA Discovery interface also features a ‘supports materials drawer’ which can be accessed in the bottom-right corner of the RDA-KB website, under ‘Support’. This features a catalogue of support materials for RDA users, including:

- **Group Guidance and Support:** e.g. guidelines for RDA members participating in WGs, including RDA rules & procedures, best practices, and publication instructions.
- **Technical documentation and instructions:** information and recommendations on the use of RDA-KB components
- **Templates, Systems, and Tools:** e.g. templates for output reports, recommended metadata schemas, and vocabulary lists
- **Additional resources:** RDA (-related) resources that are considered useful to RDA members, e.g. standards development recommendations from HSBooster.

These resources include guidelines and recommendations useful to WG members generally, including resources particularly useful for landscape analyses, such as related advice on landscape analysis publication, and which templates to use.

The RDA-KB also includes a Helpdesk, available from the bottom-right corner of the RDA-KB website, under 'Help'. This allows users to create tickets for RDA TIGER personnel relating to bug fixes, questions, feature requests, and so on.

2.2.3. RDA Annotator

The RDA Annotator³⁹ is a browser extension and service of the RDA-KB that allows RDA users to annotate text-snippets from any web-based resource with descriptions and RDA-related metadata and vocabularies. RDA groups spend a lot of time and effort searching the landscape for materials, which often need to be read and analysed in detail. Besides for what is included in the final output, the results of these laborious landscape analyses do not tend to be reused by others. This is what motivates the Annotator. The Annotator lets users save useful materials found in the process of landscape analysis, provide them with descriptions and link them to RDA vocabularies, thereby making them findable and reusable to other users via the RDA-KB.

In short, the Annotator can annotate any piece of text that the user selects on the web. The Annotator can then apply keywords, descriptions/notes, and various RDA-related vocabularies to the annotation, which contextualises and categorises the content. Annotations made using the Annotator are then passed to the RDA Graph, which can then be accessed by any user via RDA Discovery. This allows RDA users to capture useful information at a very granular level which may not make it into published reports, allowing other users to find and contextualise such information in the future. Annotations made are visible to other users as highlights in the text being browsed, and are associated with a user's ORCID account. This allows other users to identify who has produced an annotation, and to browse all annotations that they themselves have created. The Annotator is highly customisable, and can be fitted with additional vocabularies, which can then be toggled on or off by the individual user as needed. This functionality makes it particularly useful for landscape analysis efforts.

The RDA Annotator is a browser extension available for Chromium- and Firefox -based browsers, that builds on the open-source code from the annotation tool [Hypothesis.is](https://hypothesis.is).⁴⁰ The RDA Annotator is available for download via the RDA-KB website. The browser extension will be available from the Google Chrome Web Store, which will facilitate installation and updates further.⁴¹ WP4 is currently working on promoting its uptake among RDA Users through webinars⁴², and to work with select RDA WGs to identify use cases and gather feedback.

³⁹ kb-rda.org/annotator (accessed 2025.11.25)

⁴⁰ For technical documentation, see DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737222>;

For user guidelines, including installation, and use, see: Laurens, T., Hugo, W., Saldner, S. (2025). RDA Annotator: Guidelines Instructions for installing and using the RDA Annotator. Zenodo <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17772540>; also on kb-rda.org

⁴¹ The extension is currently under review by the Chrome Web Store, and should be available soon.

⁴² www.rd-alliance.org/news/welcome-to-the-rda-knowledge-base/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

Figure 4: RDA Annotator in action

2.2.4. RDA Publisher

The RDA Publisher⁴³ application assists with the publication of RDA resources (outputs, supplementary materials, or any other resource) to both Zenodo and the RDA Graph. The approach has several advantages, including the ability to accommodate more than one metadata schema that may depend on the type of content, and to link to any number of LOD-type vocabularies and registries to better contextualise the resources. This flexibility provides added future proofing, since it may eventually become necessary to publish RDA outputs elsewhere than Zenodo, which the Publisher can easily be configured to do. For example, groups may develop new formal or specific standards that may want to be preserved, even if these aren't available on Zenodo.

The DANS Frontend Framework is linked to the RDA Publisher application, which takes care of metadata and data preparation and transformation, asynchronous uploads for large files, and similar concerns. The RDA Publisher can be configured for multiple deposit targets. In the case of RDA, one might want to deposit copies of a resource to Zenodo, to a long-term preservation platform, and possibly the RDA website in one automated execution.

The RDA Graph can be thought of as an additional set of metadata, linked to a platform where these materials are published, usually Zenodo. The curated workflow serves to minimise or eliminate duplication of deposits by implementing controlled vocabulary and maintaining consistent metadata across resources so that they are traceable and findable. It also facilitates quicker publication.

⁴³ kb-rda.org/publisher

Currently, the Publisher is ready to be implemented on a technical level, but policies surrounding the implementation are being discussed in consultation with the RDA Secretariat. WP4 met with the Secretariat in April and December 2025 to discuss how the Publisher can be integrated with the workflows and procedures that the RDA uses when publishing materials. A draft workflow for publishing using the RDA Publisher has been established, and is expected to be launched in early 2026, following internal processes at the RDA..

2.3 Outreach and engagements/co-creation activities

WP4 participated in various outreach and coordination activities throughout the project.⁴⁴ This was the main source of feedback gathered during RDA Plenaries, through workshops with users, and in meetings with key stakeholders, mainly with the RDA Secretariat, and the RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB). Below is a brief overview of these engagements, and the feedback received:

Table 3. RDA Knowledge Base events, meetings, and feedback received

Event/meeting	Description
RDA P21, October 2023	First demonstration of the Knowledge Base concept with real data. The Knowledge Base received positive feedback. Options for establishing groups dedicated to maintaining RDA vocabularies were discussed.
RDA P22, May 2024	First demonstration of an early version of RDA Annotator (then referred to as The Annotation Tool/Platform ⁴⁵), together with a round of formal feedback from TIGER users.
RDA Secretariat, September 2024	Work meeting on developing a roadmap towards the launch of the Knowledge Base and its implementation into RDA workflows, website synchronisation, privacy policies, and long-term sustainability.
RDA P23, November 2024	First overview of the full suite of Knowledge Base components as a presentation at an RDA TIGER booth during the event. ⁴⁶ Included feedback from users and WGs, as well as coordination and planning with RDA Secretariat members about the implementation and sustainability issues.
RDA TAB, February 2025	Demonstration of the Knowledge Base at two TAB sessions, and discussion around potential involvement of the RDA TAB in sustainability solutions.
RDA Secretariat, April 2025	Two-day work meeting around the implementation of the RDA Publisher and integration into RDA Workflows; use and maintenance of vocabularies; role of the RDA in curating Knowledge Base data

⁴⁴ For a full overview of outreach activities in the project overall, see D6.5, section 4.2.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

⁴⁵ For details, see D4.2, annex B. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

⁴⁶ Slides presented at P23 are available at, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17752536>

Knowledge Base Beta Launch, April 2025 ⁴⁷	Introducing the beta version of the Knowledge Base to the public. The launch event included a webinar dedicated to demonstrating the Knowledge Base features. The following feedback sessions provided useful input. A Menti poll also provided useful input on what features users were interested in with the Knowledge Base. ⁴⁸
Hands-on & Feedback sessions, May 2025	Two hands-on and follow-up session were organised in early and late May following the Beta Launch. These were particularly directed at RDA WGs, and more interactive. These featured more in-depth demonstration of RDA-KB features, use-cases for RDA WGs, hands-on testing, and opportunities to provide feedback and questions.
Knowledge Base Launch & WG workshop, October 2025 ⁴⁹	Following further development using the feedback gathered from the Beta Launch events, the official Knowledge Base Launch Sessions featured demonstrations of new features, use-cases, and a Q&A session. The launch was followed by a WG workshops that went into further detail on use-cases for WGs, and provided opportunities for WG to discuss their needs and wishes for the Knowledge Base.
RDA P25, November 2025	Presenting the released version of the Knowledge Base, and collecting feedback from users and the RDA Secretariat. Feature requests, including for the inclusion of certain vocabularies were received.
RDA Secretariat work session, December 2025	Presenting the released version of the Knowledge Base, and collecting feedback from users and the RDA Secretariat. Feature requests, including for the inclusion of certain vocabularies were received.
WG Workshop, December 2025	A half-day work session with the RDA Secretariat to determine how the RDA Publisher will be integrated into the publishing procedures for RDA Groups. A draft workflow was determined, and several changes were made to the RDA Publisher relating to UI and use of vocabularies, to further adapt it to the requirements of the RDA Secretariat. Implementation is expected to follow in January 2026.

3. Progress towards outcomes identified in previous deliverables

This section tracks progress towards outcomes outlined in previous deliverable, D4.1: Description of Output Support Services and Maintenance Platform,⁵⁰ and D4.2: Performance report on the Output

⁴⁷ Event page: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-tiger-knowledge-base-beta-launch/> (accessed 01-12-2025)

⁴⁸ Collaborative notes, Menti meter results, and slides from the beta launch session and two follow-up sessions: docs.google.com/document/d/1lrd0aZqBfBXo2ExzNBhgB0hYKZX_czW-UTdF4mOPTyE/

⁴⁹ A recording of the launch webinar can be found on: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/welcome-to-the-rda-knowledge-base/> (accessed 2025.11.30)

⁵⁰ Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2023). RDA TIGER D4.1 – Description of Output Support Services and Maintenance Platform (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096631>

Support Services.⁵¹ It also summarizes lessons learned associated with each of these outcomes and processes.

Throughout this report, tables are colour-coded with final status indicators, as below.

Excluded/ Not Achievable This task or output will not be achieved or has been removed from scope.	Not Started Not started as planned, or still to be done. <i>Should be the exception.</i>	Challenges Remaining challenges, if any.	Progress Implemented and/ or available	Lessons Lessons learned and recommendations
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3.1. Progress with Solutions and Remedies for Main Concerns

3.1.1 Progress with Remedies for Identified Focus Areas

Work Package 4 in the RDA TIGER project developed a portfolio and approach to its support activities and infrastructure as reported in previous deliverables (D4.1 - Description of Output Support Services and Knowledge Base [4], and D4.2 - Performance report on the Output Support Services). In these deliverables, a number of broad issues, problems, desirable outcomes, and design considerations associated with RDA management of its corpus, and of RDA Working Groups that WP4 should focus on were identified. In this section, we report on progress and challenges, if any, what the final status is, and summarise the lessons learned from the effort.

3.1.1.1 Curation-Related

Table 4. Curation-Related Focus Areas

#	Focus	Description	Status and Challenges
1.1.1.1	Inconsistent Metadata	Over time, the publication of RDA outputs and supporting materials have been subject to change, and as a result, not all outputs and supplementary materials have similar metadata or a consistent curation process applied to them.	Status: A consistent metadata schema, aligned with Zenodo/ DataCite schema, but also extended to accommodate RDA-specific vocabularies has been published, and implemented in the RDA-KB and the RDA Graph for all current outputs and support materials
		Lessons learned: lack of consistency of description of outputs and support materials over time built up significant technical debt, and required considerable effort (human curation) to correct. Current practices at the secretariat, published metadata schema, and publisher tools available from RDA TIGER address this	

⁵¹ Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2024). RDA TIGER D4.2 – Performance report on the Output Support Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

		adequately.	
1.1.1.2	Generalised Metadata	RDA outputs have been published to Zenodo for about 6 years now, and in such cases the minimum metadata associated with Zenodo/ DataCite publications are required. This metadata is generalised, and unless the depositor adds appropriate (and unmanaged) tags, RDA-specific elements are not accommodated in metadata.	Status: All legacy outputs have been processed and provided with missing metadata where appropriate.
		Lessons learned: address at source - provision of metadata prior to publication is highly preferable. Adequate measures are in place at the secretariat to achieve this.	
1.1.1.3	Multiple repositories	RDA has used multiple repositories for both outputs and other supplementary materials over time. At present, all publications go to Zenodo, but this may not be the case for all outputs in future.	Status: All new deposits of outputs and supplementary materials will go to Zenodo, and all legacy resources - whether in RDA website, Zenodo, or elsewhere in the web has now been curated and included into one searchable catalogue.
		Lessons learned: A future situation may arise again requiring the ability to publish RDA resources in multiple repositories. The RDA Knowledge Base is designed with this in mind.	
1.1.1.4	Collection Management	The RDA has established two collections in Zenodo, one for formal outputs, and one for supplementary materials. Both these collections appear somewhat variable in terms of content despite a moderation requirement for deposits to the collections.	Status: All legacy deposits in Zenodo have now been correctly classified as one of a number of resource types, correcting past mistakes.
		Lessons learned: address at source - a single point of moderation is highly desirable. Adequate measures are in place at the secretariat to achieve this.	
1.1.1.5	Long-Term Preservation	Outputs that are maintained and made available from the RDA website have very limited preservation certainty, and those published in Zenodo are likely to be preserved but Zenodo does not explicitly provide a long-term preservation service aligned with trustworthy repository criteria.	Status: The RDA Publisher developed inter alia for RDA allows deposit of content to multiple targets, of which a suitable long-term repository can be one.
			Challenges: Decisions on whether Zenodo is considered adequate for long-term preservation (LTP), and to migrate non-Zenodo deposits need to be taken by the RDA secretariat.

		Recommendation: The RDA secretariat needs to decide on a secondary (mirror) deposit of content for purposes of redundancy, if not for LTP, assuming Zenodo provides adequate long-term preservation functionality and sustainability.
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3.1.1.2 Process-Related

Table 5. Process-Related Focus Areas

#	Focus	Description	Status and Challenges
1.1.2.1	Research Methodology	Recent improvements in annotation of web-based resources has implications for research methodology and management of references that can be included into working group practices.	Status: An annotation tool is available for use by RDA members, annotating web content with RDA vocabulary, and its use has been promoted in webinars. A final engagement is required with WGs to promote future use.
		Lessons learned: Working groups approach their efforts in many ways, and the support tooling can only accommodate a specific set of approaches. Some convergence on standardised ways of working will be required in future.	
1.1.2.2	Landscape Analysis	Similarly, most Working Groups need to do some form of landscape analysis, and this is repeated without benefiting from similar analysis done within RDA or in associated initiatives in the landscape.	Status: A sample of RDA TIGER landscape assessments have been imported into the catalogue (see Figure 4) and it is expected that future landscape analyses will be added to the corpus.
		Lessons learned: As above	
1.1.2.3	Mobilisation and Re-use of Web Resources	WG effort expended in reviewing resources is often not re-usable except with some difficulty, given that at most the resources will be made available as references.	Status: Toolset (RDA Annotator and RDA Discovery) is available.
		Challenges: A request to accommodate reference manager exports was made by end users late in the project life cycle, but an effort will still be made to accommodate the request.	
		Lessons learned: As above	
1.1.2.4	Structuring of Recommendations	Recommendations, best practices, and guidelines are commonly reported in monolithic documents, making it difficult to find and re-use.	Status: Best practice guidelines were included into the guidance developed in support of the RDA Knowledge Base.
		Lessons learned: Uptake will be very slow, and guidance on working group best	

		practices need to be promoted more aggressively.	
1.1.2.5	Publication Process	The publication process for RDA outputs and supplementary materials is not standardised, and has changed over time.	Status: Discussion on the need for standardisation with the RDA Secretariat has been completed, guidance document has been developed, and a single process is already followed..
		Lessons learned: Maintain a single process for publication of outputs and other resources in future.	
1.1.2.6	Dissemination Channels	RDA outputs are disseminated primarily via the RDA website, and there is limited possibility for third-party applications to access and use the corpus of RDA work in a different environment.	Status: Single catalogue has now been implemented.
			Challenges: Harvesting from ElasticSearch Catalogue to be tested, using standard APIs.
		Recommendation: Open ElasticSearch API for external users.	
1.1.2.7	Re-Use and Impact	Dissemination channel options, and partial publication of RDA outputs with persistent identifiers leads to limitations on re-use and gathering of metrics in respect of re-use.	Status: All future resources will be published in Zenodo, with a DataCite DOI. DataCite provides citation metrics.
		Recommendation: Apply DataCite citation indices and metrics to determine impact. If resources are published without a DataCite DOI, republish with a DataCite DOI via Zenodo.	

3.1.1.3 Standards-Related

Table 6. Standards-Related Focus areas

#	Focus	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.3.1	Precision	The precision that can be expected of annotation increases significantly with standardisation of the vocabularies used for tagging.	Status: This aspect has been fully implemented, and new vocabularies can easily be added via configuration of the RDA Annotation Tool.
		Lessons learned: Working Groups more often than not developed their own classification systems (vocabularies), and a generalised vocabulary management capability is required to accommodate this.	

1.1.3.2	Metadata Standards	Standards for metadata applicable to different types of RDA outputs will improve interoperability and reusability.	Status: This aspect has also been fully addressed via standardisation of RDA Metadata.
		Lessons learned: Metadata standards are important and should be actively maintained by an RDA structure - e.g. RDA TAB.	
1.1.3.3	Templates, Branding, and Version Management	Standards for presentations, reports, recommendations, and the minimum content, branding, and versioning information for each of these will improve the image, reusability, and quality of the outputs.	Status: This is addressed through the following support documentation outputs (see table 2 for further details): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WG Welcome Pack - WG Guidelines, incl publishing - Publication Guidelines - Templates, metadata

3.1.1.4 Complexity and Granularity

Table 7. Complexity and Granularity -Related Focus areas

#	Focus	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.4.1	Complex Landscape	RDA working groups need to be able to reuse what has been done before, and find it easily: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • what should be considered in the Case Statements; • who is working on this subject area in the global Open Science (OS) landscape; • who in RDA may have the necessary expertise and interest to contribute. 	Status: The data to find experts within the RDA membership on a given subject or domain has been curated and de-duplicated. Moreover, all available annotations, resources, organisations, and individuals can be found via search and discovery. Outputs, groups, and members are automatically synchronised with the RDA-KB
		Lessons learned: End users do not necessarily consider these capabilities when a WG starts out - include explicitly in guidance with some examples.	
1.1.4.2	Proliferation of Guidance and Outputs	There is a significant body of published work on best practices, guidance, and recommendations in respect of a wide variety of topics of interest to the community. As yet, there is no real attempt to consolidate, standardise, and collate these resources to avoid duplication, divergence, and maximise return from these investments, or to make them machine-readable and actionable.	Status: Opportunities are sought in new project proposals to employ a part-AI-based approach to annotation of these resources.

		Recommendation: continue to include bulk annotation with AI assistance into project proposals.	
1.1.4.3	Buried Recommendations	Moreover, many of the recommendations, best practices, and guidance are reported within deliverables and outputs that are linked to project websites and structures, and as such are often not published in mainstream channels. Such reports seldom result in widely adopted recommendations or specifications governed by organisations such as ISO ⁵² , W3C, or IETF.	Status: Saving and making such resources available to others are an ideal use case for the RDA Annotator: snippets of text pertaining to e.g. recommendations can be tagged as such using appropriate vocabularies, and made available to other users via the RDA Annotator.
		Recommendation: Promote (consistent) use of the RDA Annotator for use on buried recommendations. The prior recommendations also applied here.	

3.1.1.5 Capacity

Table 8. Capacity-Related Focus areas

#	Focus	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.5.1	Voluntary Contributions	Working Groups are largely resourced via voluntary contributions from members, and in most cases only a few workgroup members contribute to the main body of work in the working group.	Status: The tools and services that the RDA-KB provides should in principle facilitate work by WG members, however resource limitations remain a factor.
		Lessons learned: RDA WGs are continually resource-constrained in terms of funding, time, and human resources. See section 4, point 1 for details.	
1.1.5.2	Bias and Skewed Resources	Resources are sometimes available due to overlap and synergy with funded tasks and outcomes in which workgroup members participate. On the one hand, this contributes funded resources to the working group, but on the other hand, it results in disproportionate contributions from these sources - not always therefore a balanced view or broad consensus.	Status: The improved findability provided by the RDA-KB, including availability of WP3 landscape efforts should make it easier to identify potential biases by WG members, e.g. by making it easier to track publication history, and affiliations.
		Recommendation: promote awareness on these issues, including guidance on mitigation	

⁵² ISO as a standards body may present other challenges: for example standards are not openly accessible by default.

1.1.5.3	Content Focus	Working Groups tend to focus on and have intentions to create content (a set of recommendations, a specification) and do not have capacity, experience, or incentives to look at other aspects of product readiness: communication, adoption, dissemination, standards creation, and so on.	Status: Guidance on these issues have been provided through the RDA-KB Support Documentation Drawer.
		Recommendation: Guidance materials can be expanded further, especially on aspects around communication. Lessons learned through other project work packages regarding these and other issues should be included here.	
1.1.5.4	Capital and Operating Expenditure	RDA receives most of its ‘capital expenditure’ for free, by way of voluntary contributions of members (many of whom are funded indirectly via grants or their institutions to participate). It is not feasible to rely on voluntary maintenance of RDA assets (outputs, especially) via the same mechanism: grants often do not focus on these activities, and maintenance cannot be left to ad-hoc arrangements.	Status: The possibility of creating a permanent body within the RDA responsible for such maintenance issues has been discussed between the project and the RDA, but has not yet yielded results. Such a body would likely rely heavily on voluntary contributions as well, limiting their capacity to do continuous maintenance work.
		Recommendation: Further explore opportunities to institute maintenance bodies, potentially in collaboration/synergy with other projects.	

3.1.1.6 Objectives

Table 9. Objectives-Related Focus areas

#	Objective	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.6.1	Improved Quality	There is a need to make sure that all WG outputs meet minimum quality standards, and that these improve over time. Minimum quality standards include metadata schema adherence, using templates, and following guidelines and procedures.	Progress: An initial set of procedures and guidance has been developed. Working Groups supported by the RDA TIGER project have all reported a positive impact. ⁵³ RDA Secretariat is the final arbiter of submission quality.
		No additional comments.	
1.1.6.2	Improved Usefulness	Usefulness of outputs are dependent on the perspective of the end-user, and working groups are expected to align with identified needs and expectations of the community. At least some	Progress: To the extent that the findability and usability objective can be served by technical means, the goal has been achieved.

⁵³ See D6.5, section 3.2 for results from WG feedback: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>

		usability is a direct result of standardisation and presentation (e.g. machine-readability, findability).	
		Lessons learned: ultimately, improvement in usability and findability depend on the effort put into metadata and annotation by WG members, and without some support mechanism similar to that of RDA TIGER, this effort is likely to be highly variable.	
1.1.6.3	Proper Maintenance	Proper maintenance and curation of RDA outputs after publication - in the short term and in respect of long-term preservation - is not addressed adequately in current working group obligations - essentially an optional aspect of RDA member activity.	Progress: Possibility of 'Worker Groups' was raised at P21, and well received.
		Recommendation: establish a 'worker group' in RDA to maintain and disseminate the assets created in RDA TIGER.	
1.1.6.4	Improved Sustainability	Sustainability of RDA outputs may have to be evaluated against emerging principles for open scholarly infrastructure, for example as exemplified by POSI.	Excluded/ Not Achievable:
		No additional comments.	

3.1.2 Working Group Workflow and Processes

From D4.1: "Historically, RDA Working Groups have generated outputs in a non-standardised way, and the scope, granularity, and composition of the outputs were largely left to the working group to decide. This has advantages, since being too prescriptive can lead to limitations on working group creativity, and standardisation places a burden on voluntary effort to ensure compliance. As a result, working group outputs have been diverse. Moreover, maintenance is currently also voluntary, and there is no certainty that outputs will be maintained, or progress to wider adoption vis. standards authorities such as ISO, IETF, or W3C."

Work Package 4 in RDA TIGER aims to address these deficiencies, at least in part, by creating solution elements that contribute to steps in the workflow, and below, we report on progress in this regard.

Table 10: Updated progress in respect of workflow support in RDA TIGER

#	Objective	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.2.1	Preparation	Standardisation of the way in which workgroups do their research to maximise its reusability, and upfront	Progress: guidance in this respect has been included into support materials available to new groups.

		guidance in respect of structuring and standardisation of outputs and supplementary materials.	
		Recommendation: establish a 'worker group' in RDA to maintain and disseminate the assets created in RDA TIGER.	
1.2.2	Service support for WGs	(Facilitation, communication, landscape analysis and direct support services): These aspects will not be addressed by WP4, but by other activities in RDA TIGER. Optional 3rd-party grants allocated to selected working groups may require guidance and support from WP4.	N/A
1.2.3	Finalisation	This step will require direct assistance and support from WP4, ensuring proper publication, structuring, annotation, and dissemination of outputs, web-based resources referenced or created by the working group, and relevant supplementary materials.	Progress: This task is currently performed by the secretariat, with a decision to allow publication by group chairs to be taken in the future.
		Lessons learned: This is a good decision, given that it required significant effort to bring all RDA resources to the same standard of curation. Once processes and the RDA-KB is well established, responsibility can be delegated to group chairs.	
1.2.4	Maintenance	The RDA TIGER project also has a finite existence, but structures and procedures for maintenance of RDA outputs need to be considered and established during the lifetime of the project.	Progress: Possibility of 'Worker Groups' was raised at P21, and well received.
		Recommendation: establish a 'worker group' in RDA to maintain and disseminate the assets created in RDA TIGER.	
1.2.5	Adoption	Likewise, the RDA TIGER project does not have in scope to facilitate the adoption of outputs formally in standards organisations such as ISO or W3C, but the process to do so can be established, agreed with relevant standards organisations, and included into WG guidance and procedures.	Progress: Contact has been made with HSBooster ⁵⁴ , and they have contributed a guideline for groups to consider at inception.
		Lessons learned: The advisory obtained from the expert group is useful, but should ideally be extended to cover procedural aspects of publication as W3C	

⁵⁴ <https://www.hsbooster.eu/about-0>

		or ISO standards.	
1.2.6	Standardisation of Legacy Outputs	RDA has historically produced outputs that are not standardised, and funding or collaboration opportunities need to be found to address this.	Progress: Several releases of improved and standardised resources (outputs, supplementary materials) have been made to date. No need for funding. Automated synchronisation with the RDA website is in place.
		Lessons learned: the level of curation currently in place can easily deteriorate again without active curation and preservation.	
1.2.7	Crowdsourcing	It will be possible for any interested party to contribute to the annotation effort, and initially, RDA members and participating institutions provide a starting point.	Progress: Technical infrastructure and support documentation is in place to accommodate this aspect within RDA.
		Lessons learned: uptake to date is limited, and dissemination and awareness raising efforts will have to be maintained after the end of the project.	
1.2.8	EOSC Focus	This will require engagement with current EOSC projects and initiatives to maximise the standardisation of their future outputs.	Progress: Technical infrastructure is in place to accommodate this aspect, and the project is ready to engage HE projects and EOSC task forces in this regard. A landscape analysis of EU-related impacts (EOSC, HE) has been completed and will be uploaded as bulk annotations.
		Lessons learned: These links and associations will require future periodic updates that will have to be included into the tasks of maintenance and support personnel.	

3.2 Alignment with Work In Progress

Table 11: Status of alignment with work in progress

#	Objective	Description	Progress and Challenges
2.1.1	Landscape Service	The Landscape Service consists of two major components: the development and maintenance of the database containing landscape analyses, and the delivery of the actual landscape analyses to the WGs.	Progress: Landscape Analysis items have now been included into the RDA catalogue, and in future, can be updated via the RDA Annotation Plug-In.
		Recommendation: in future, landscape analysis will be largely dependent on continued contributions of annotations by groups. This process requires direction and support.	
2.1.2	RDA Knowledge Base	RDA TIGER will make use of and further refine the RDA Knowledge Base.	Progress: Final release will be in December 2025.
		No additional comments	
2.1.2.1	Provision of a Helpdesk and Service Level Support	Assisting users with queries, problems, issues, and suggestions for improvement, measured against a service-level agreement in terms of response and resolution time.	Progress: Implemented, and will continue with a revised SLA at completion of the RDA TIGER project.
		Recommendation: Future support is based on the sustainability planning prepared by the RDA TIGER project.	
2.1.2.2	Issue and Request Resolution	Providing functional controller and developer support for resolution of technical system issues, resolving non-technical issues with assistance and contribution from RDA Secretariat staff.	Progress This is possible via the helpdesk, or via email (most suggestions for improvement from the TIGER users have been received via email). These issues are prioritised and implemented as they are registered.
		Recommendation: As above.	
2.1.2.3	Limited New Functionality Development	A prioritised list of new feature requests to be maintained from the ticket system, together with estimates of time and effort, system impact. If maintenance time is not taken up by issue resolution, the team can implement new features;	Progress This process started after the beta release, and will continue based on the sustainability plan proposed by the project.
		Recommendation: As above.	

2.1.2.4	Technical Workshops at RDA Events	Provision of one or more workshops peripheral to RDA events (plenaries) to coach and support system users.	Progress A number of events were arranged in the last year of the project to disseminate information about the RDA Knowledge Base.
		Recommendation: As above.	
2.2.1	Basic Infrastructure	The RDA Knowledge Base provides a basic set of tools and infrastructure.	Progress Implemented and available
		No additional comments.	
2.2.2	Landscape Extension	This can and will be extended to accommodate the needs of RDA TIGER for landscape-related links.	Progress Implemented and available
		No additional comments.	
2.2.3	Object Extension	Extended within RDA to accommodate other digital objects that need to be managed	Progress These entities are now managed in the new RDA website, and integrated/ included as facets for discovery.
		Recommendation: The new RDA website is the most appropriate location for managing groups, members, and organisations.	
2.2.4	Casting the net wider	Standardising the annotation and availability of domain knowledge about research data and code infrastructure and its management in a formal 'Body of Knowledge'	Excluded/ Not Achievable In scope: engaging HE projects and EOSC Task Forces to contribute. Specifically engage FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC.
		Lessons learned: It proved complex to find time and opportunity to engage external projects to motivate the use of tools developed in RDA TIGER.	
2.3	Graph Database	"The work to establish vocabularies and graph infrastructure for use by WP4, based on 2.1 above, is well advanced and a first release can be expected at the end of June 2023."	Status: This has been available since the beta release in late 2023.
		No further comments.	

3.3. Status: Scope and Nature of Planned Solutions

The following tables lists the proposed solutions and tools that were planned for use in WP4 to support RDA Working Groups, and outlined in D4.1. In the table, the solutions are described, and current status is assessed in terms of progress and challenges/ next steps (if any).

3.3.1 Policy and Procedures

Table 12. Policy and Procedures Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.1.1	Policy - Outputs	RDA will benefit from a policy in respect of output production and publication - dealing with aspects such as licensing and access, branding, ownership, attribution, and maintenance.	Status: Recommended policy amendments have been shared with the secretariat.
		Lessons Learned: The secretariat is resource-constrained in terms of both funding and personnel, and as a result, have very little time to devote to new initiatives and processes.	
3.1.2	Procedure: Workgroup Creation and Life Cycle	This exists to some degree, but must be reviewed in the light of additional support materials, guidelines, mechanisms, and tools required for the ' Output Definition Report ', and must align with policy ⁵⁵ .	Progress: Recommended process amendments have been shared with the secretariat.
		Lessons Learned: As above	
3.1.3	Procedure: Research Processes	Procedures for annotation and referencing of resources and publications in the course of the workgroup's activities.	Progress: Recommended process amendments have been shared with the secretariat and included into WG support materials.
		Lessons Learned: Uptake and dissemination has proven difficult, indicating that without dedicated support, such as provided by RDA TIGER, groups are unlikely to take guidance into account.	
3.1.4	Procedure: Publication of Outputs	RDA Working Groups need to adopt a common procedure for publication of outputs and supplementary materials, based on the RDA Knowledge Base.	Progress: Recommended process amendments have been shared with the secretariat, supplementing procedures already in place.
		No additional comments.	

⁵⁵ Clarity is needed from RDA on how this differs from Case Statements required from new groups. Needs to be differentiated clearly.

3.1.5	Procedure: Curation of RDA Collections	RDA collections in Zenodo [2],[3] need accession procedures that will ensure consistency of materials and resources in the collections.	Progress: Recommended process amendments have been shared with the secretariat, supplementing procedures already in place.
		Lessons Learned: As for 3.1.1.	
		The process whereby RDA identifies vocabulary and how it is governed and maintained must be documented.	Progress: Recommended sources of truth have been shared with the secretariat.
		Lessons Learned: Assigning future responsibility for curation has proven to be difficult, since most contributors to RDA are volunteers (RDA TIGER has recommended that the TAB assumes this role, possibly delegating it to a dedicated group).	

3.3.2 Standards and Benchmarks

Table 13. Standards and Benchmarks Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.2.1	Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies	RDA needs to use standard APIs and encodings for its own vocabularies.	Progress: Preliminary, curated lists are available.
		Lessons Learned: The hosting of such vocabularies will be problematic, and will have to be implemented in, for example, a GitHub repository, w3id.org, or a similar public resource to avoid additional resource burdens for RDA.	
3.2.2	Preferred Formats for Dissemination and Preservation	These are needed to maximise utility for the community and to ensure long-term preservation.	Progress: These have been defined.
		Lessons Learned: The list will require occasional maintenance by a dedicated group in RDA.	
3.2.3	Annotation Standards and Schema	RDA will define a number of standard schemas: metadata, rating, and landscape context are examples.	Progress: A basic annotation schema has been defined.
		Lessons Learned: As above.	
3.2.4	Minimum Metadata Schema	These have to be differentiated for different output and resource types, while satisfying repository and RDA requirements.	Progress: Metadata schema has been defined.

		Lessons Learned: As above.	
3.2.5	Templates for Output Reports, Recommendations, Standards and Specifications	A number of standardised templates are needed for typical RDA outputs and supporting materials. One objective is to simplify annotation and machine-readability.	Progress: The procedures defined by the secretariat have been extended with additional guidance.
		Lessons Learned: As above - will require maintenance by a dedicated group in RDA.	

3.3.3 Systems and Tools

Table 14. Systems and Tool Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.3.1	RDA Knowledge Base	The RDA Knowledge Base plays a central role in support of WGs and associated RDA activities: publication, annotation, discovery, and preservation.	Progress: Available.
		Lessons Learned: Additional dissemination and awareness activities will have to be continued for new groups in RDA.	
3.3.2	Reference Managers	Integration between mainstream Reference Managers and the RDA-KB will benefit end-users.	Excluded/ Not Achievable
		Recommendation: attempt to implement in final activities of RDA TIGER WP4.	
3.3.3	Annotation Platforms	Integration with annotation platforms such as hypothes.is will broaden the scope of end users and extend the RDA graph/ knowledge base.	Progress: We have tested the integration, and the RDA annotator is based on hypothes.is code. Can be implemented if required in future.
		No additional comments.	
3.3.4	Helpdesk	The Helpdesk assists working groups and other RDA members to request assistance with tools, software, templates, or any other solution element	Progress: Helpdesk available.
		No additional comments.	
3.3.5	Helpdesk	The guidance and support	Progress: Available

	Knowledge Base	materials (below) serve as an entry point to the policies, procedures, standards, tools, and best practices available to working groups. These are made available as HelpDesk knowledge base articles, in addition to being published and annotated.	
No additional comments.			
3.3.6	The 'RDA Graph'	The need to accommodate a wider set of entities, concepts, and relations emanating from RDA within its landscape and ecosystem has to be accommodated: largely by providing access to additional schema, vocabularies and registries as a basis for annotation.	Progress: The operational version is deployed in PostgreSQL as a 'graph-ready' database, with all graph nodes and relationships explicitly captured. Export to a graph is simple to implement.
Recommendation: retain as is, since there has been no direct requests for a graph representation of the data to be made available.			

3.3.4 Guidance and Support

Table 15. Guidance and Support Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.4.1	Guidelines: Workgroup Establishment	Description of life cycle, which solution elements are available for and should be used in each step of the life cycle.	Progress: Guidance is linked to group life cycle and is available.
Lessons Learned: Additional dissemination and awareness activities will have to be continued for new groups in RDA.			
3.4.2	Guidelines: Maximising Workgroup Effort	Includes landscape analysis support, annotation best practices, structuring of outputs and supplementary materials, making effort reusable - overlaps with the previous, but adds guidelines for annotation of web resources.	Progress: Documented guidelines are available.
Lessons Learned: As above.			
3.4.3	Documenting	It is anticipated that standards	Progress

	Standards and Specifications	and specifications will be occasional outputs from working groups, and to ensure that these are documented in a consistent and publishable way, a template with attendant guidance will be developed for this aspect. WP4 will endeavour to make use of EU-funded support services for this ⁵⁶ .	HSBooster provided guidelines.
Lessons Learned: As above.			
3.4.4	Standards Authority Adoption Guidelines	Further support of the process of creating and disseminating standards and specifications: guidance will be developed, in consultation with e.g. ISO and W3C to guide working groups on processes to formally adopt their work. Will also make use of EU-funded support services where applicable ⁴ .	Excluded/ Not Achievable
Recommendation: This guidance is important, and should be considered as a topic for future improvements.			
3.4.5	Informal Contributions to the 'RDA Graph'	It is possible and desirable for individual RDA members to annotate, rate, and comment materials referenced and produced by RDA. To assist with this, a guidance document will be developed.	Progress: Annotation is possible at the present time.
Lessons Learned: using annotations as a findable and reusable record of activity represents a shift in work method for most RDA contributors, and the cultural change aspect has been underestimated by WP4.			

3.3.5 Capacity Enhancement, Training, and Service Assistance

Table 16. Capacity Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.5.1	Workshops: Workgroup Output Support	Training materials and plenary-aligned workshops to highlight and introduce the	Progress: Several events have been arranged. See record of events in 2.6.

⁵⁶ <https://www.hsbooster.eu/>

		support mechanisms developed by RDA TIGER.	
		Lessons learned: The format and duration of these events (online, 1 hour) are not intensive enough to result in confident adoption by participants.	
3.5.2	Service Assistance: Curation	Curation activities for Working Groups to publish their efforts and outputs in the recommended way.	Progress: Engagement was established with three WGs, and their annotations will be included into the RDA-KB as examples.
		Lessons learned: The engagement process should have started earlier in the project.	

3.4. Implementation

3.4.1 Progress with implementation

The work in RDA TIGER WP4 has largely achieved (and, in some cases have gone beyond) the scope that was envisaged at the commencement of the project.

3.4.2 Record of Releases

Table 17. Plenary-aligned activities

Plenary	Main Objectives	Status
P21	Disseminate procedures in respect of Research Processes and Curation of RDA Collections	Status: Completed
	Standardise Preferred Formats for Dissemination and Preservation, and Minimum Metadata Schema	Status: Completed
	Implement the RDA Knowledge Base, Helpdesk, and Helpdesk Knowledge Base	Status: A first release of the RDA-KB was published as a beta version with sample data (release 1) in July 2023.
	Publish guidelines for Workgroup Establishment	Status: Draft guidelines available.
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	Excluded/ Not Achievable
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	Status: Manual curation.
P22	Implement the Annotation Platform	Status: Beta version available

	Publish guidelines for Maximising Workgroup Effort	Progress: Draft guidelines available
	Operationalise and explain Informal Contributions to the 'RDA Graph'	Excluded/ Not Achievable
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	Excluded/ Not Achievable
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	Status: Curation team is in place, and support materials and infrastructure are ready to offer a service.

3.4.3 Timelines and Dependencies - Revised

Due to a delay of approximately 6 months in having a production-ready dataset integrated with the new RDA website, some of the Plenary-related activities have to be rescheduled. This revised activity and implementation plan is summarised below.

Table 18: Revised Implementation Plan

Plenary	Main Objectives	Planning
Pre-P23	Disseminate procedures in respect of Research Processes and Curation of RDA Collections	Status: Available in support materials published with RDA knowledge Base
P23	Disseminate procedures for Workgroup Creation and Life Cycle, and for Selection and Maintenance of Vocabulary	
	Disseminate procedures in respect of Research Processes and Curation of RDA Collections	Status: Discussions started with TAB/ Secretariat, and events planned.
	Publish and introduce community maintenance of Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies, as well as Annotation Standards and Schema	
	Release an updated version of the RDA Knowledge Base, and the Helpdesk Knowledge Base	Status: Release 4 available.
	Publish guidelines on Documenting Standards and Specifications, and on Standards Authority Adoption	Status: HSBooster inputs reviewed and made available.
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	Status: Publicised at P23 and hands-on demonstrations provided to interested parties at the RDA Europe booth.
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	Status: Ongoing from P23 onwards
P24	Publish and disseminate an RDA Policy on Output	Status. Outputs remain available for use

	and an updated Minimum Metadata Schema	by the community.
	Release integration of Reference Managers and external Annotation Platforms	Status: Deferred
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	Status: Deferred
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	Status: Deferred
P25	Launch Event - operational release is available and presented to the RDA community.	Status: presented in plenary and supported by availability of demonstrator at the RDA Europe booth.
Post-P25	Release integration of Reference Managers and external Annotation Platforms	Status: Under way for completion in December 2025.
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	Status: One more event planned by the end of the project.
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	Status: bulk annotation of selected WG outputs - support to be added.
	Automated synchronisation with the RDA website in place.	Status: update scripts are in place, full automation to be operationalised by the end of the project.

3.5. Exploitation Opportunities

The resources and assets established by the RDA TIGER project are already of use in other HE-funded environments, and there is potential for additional uses that have been proposed and/ or identified. These co-creation and exploitation opportunities have several benefits, amongst other by improving the return on investment in code and infrastructure, and also ensuring better sustainability by involving a wider set of individuals and organisations in the improvement and extension of the open source code repositories underpinning the work.

Table 19: Co-development and Exploitation Opportunities

RD KB Component	Completed		In Progress			Planned/ Other
	RDA TIGER	FC4E/ F-I	OSTRails	EDEN/ FIDELIS	EOSC Data Commons	
Search and Discovery	#1	#5	#6	#7	#8	#10
Configurable UI Forms	#2	#5		#7	#8	
RDA Publisher	#3	#5		#7	#8	#9
Annotator	#4			#7	#8	

#: Opportunities as listed below.

The following list explains these opportunities in more detail:

1. The Search and discovery mechanism is used in RDA TIGER for multiple dashboard and catalogue views - resources (including annotations), individuals, and organisations.
2. Configurable UI Forms are used in RDA TIGER to compose forms for metadata capture on deposit and submission to Zenodo, and for capturing the content of an annotation.
3. The RDA Publisher is used to prepare metadata and content for submission to Zenodo.
4. The Annotation Tool is used in RDA TIGER to annotate the RDA Graph with resources useful to RDA groups - focusing initially on landscape analysis, but extending in future to any reusable research conducted by RDA groups.
5. FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT make use of the same components, except for the Annotation Tool, in two streams of work.
 - a. The [Compliance Assessment Toolkit](#) (WP2) in FAIRCORE4EOSC uses the Search and Discovery component in two additional roles: to provide a catalogue of PID services compliant with EOSC PID Policy, and to provide a catalogue of the characteristics and features of PID services for purposes of selection by end users.
 - b. The Configurable UI Form and RDA Publisher is used by FAIRCORE4EOSC (WP6) to demonstrate the dual deposit of research outputs to multiple target repositories - based on a common metadata schema, datasets are deposited to Dataverse, and code is deposited to Software Heritage, with mutual updates of linked identifiers.
6. The OSTRails project uses the Search and Discovery component to find guidance, tests, metrics, criteria, and FAIR-compliant objects in the FAIR Assessment space, with extension to accommodate domain-specific nuances and refinements (for example as in FAIR Implementation Profiles).
7. The [EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS](#) projects will use the search and discovery, publisher, and annotation tools to establish a registry of trustworthy repositories in EOSC.
8. The [EOSC Data Commons](#) project will use all the available components to establish a Tools Registry, a Type Registry, and a FAIR Assessment Platform for use by repositories in the project.
9. Several other projects make use of the same components (again with the exception of the Annotation Tool). For example, the nationally funded OH-SMART project in the Netherlands makes use of the Configurable UI Form and the RDA Publisher, and were the original funders of these two components. It has since implemented many refinements that can in future be useful in a wider context - including pre-submission quality assurance (for example verifying file formats and converting them if required). It also supports metadata transformation to suit the target repository, as needed, but the RDA TIGER case does not need this at the present time.
10. The Search and Discovery component has been introduced by DANS as a possible technology base for several EU funding call proposals - including use as an inventory tool for a catalogue of best practices and recommendations in respect of data quality and reusability, and for quality and FAIR assessment.

4. Lessons Learned and Recommendations

4.1 Lessons Learned

The RDA and its groups are continually resource-constrained, in three respects:

1. **Funding:** It is, for example, not feasible for RDA to fund continued support, maintenance, and refinement of the RDA Knowledge Base, despite it being commissioned and funded originally by the RDA;
2. **Time:** since the overwhelming contribution to RDA activities and outputs are based on voluntary contributions from individuals, their time and availability is at a premium, and this aspect as a limitation on the extent to which one would be able to rely on crowdsourced contributions and on availability for capacity building was underestimated;
3. **Baseline human resources:** the RDA Secretariat has very limited capacity, and any extension of refinement to their responsibilities need to be carefully considered and not assumed to be achievable. Likewise, the TAB could nominally be considered as a representative of the community, and asked to provide governance and oversight of the RDA Knowledge Base on their behalf, but since the TAB is also based on voluntary contributions, individuals are reluctant to commit to additional responsibilities.

Aspects related to work culture change, adoption, and dissemination of RDA TIGER tools and guidance proved to be more difficult to achieve than anticipated.

4. Working Groups members, despite support from RDA TIGER, have limited time and capacity to devote to RDA-related tasks; as a result, it is not easy to disseminate new concepts, guidance, and tools.
5. Similarly, uptake of new possibilities for structuring work and outputs have been slow.
6. Working groups display a wide variety of approaches to their task, and while constraining this freedom should be avoided, the diversity also makes it complex to develop tools and guidance, since the resources to accommodate the diversity will always be limited.
7. Working groups are also likely to develop their own classifications and vocabularies, and hence a generalised and extensible way to accommodate this in the RDA Knowledge Base will be required.
8. It became clear in engagements with Working groups during the last year of the project that bulk annotation capabilities would be the preferred mechanism for publication of workgroup efforts in landscape analysis and fine-grained recommendations or specifications. This aspect is being addressed.

Correcting a corpus of RDA resources (outputs, supporting materials, and other web resources such as annotation) to all reflect a common standard of curation proved to be quite time-consuming and difficult, making it imperative not to let the current standard of curation slip in future. This aspect requires close governance and facilitation by the RDA Secretariat (see recommendations below). Detailed aspects include:

9. It is commonly agreed that curation at the time of publication is best for ensuring consistent quality, and the secretariat has processes in place to ensure this.
10. Having a single point of quality assurance at the secretariat, as is the case now, is the only way to ensure consistency.

11. Improvement in usability and findability depend on the effort put into metadata and annotation by WG members, and without some support mechanism similar to that of RDA TIGER, this effort is likely to be highly variable, and probably will diminish in future.

Finally, on a more general level, it is worth noting that it is difficult to propose a credible sustainability strategy that would be acceptable for the RDA community.

12. Project-based funding will continue to introduce uncertainties at timescales that are needed for cultural change and adoption of new routines and working practices.
13. On the other hand, fee-carrying solutions or corporate sponsorship/collaboration would risk alienating large parts of the community, or going against the open science nature of the RDA.
14. The issue is especially acute with technical artefacts (software and IT services) that require consistent maintenance, including bug fixes, security updates, and feature improvements.

4.2 Recommendations

1. Publication to multiple repositories is possible in future, since this feature is simple to implement in the Publisher component. This capability should remain in place, since future outputs could include peer-reviewed publications and formal specifications.
2. A single point of quality assurance of submissions to RDA-supported repositories (such as Zenodo) should remain in place, even if submissions are prepared by group chairs in future, as intended for the Publisher.
3. The RDA secretariat needs to decide on a secondary (mirror) deposit of content for purposes of redundancy, if not for long-term preservation (assuming Zenodo provides adequate LTP functionality and sustainability for the present).
4. RDA groups that contribute to the RDA Knowledge Base in some way (publications, annotations) should be encouraged to follow one of a number of supported processes intended to simplify inclusion of their work into the RDA-KB. This needs to be an ongoing process, especially considering that new groups are formed all the time, without the benefit in future of direct or indirect RDA TIGER support.
5. Maintenance tasks that should be governed by the RDA Community via the TAB, and could be delegated to a new dedicated group in the RDA, include:
 - a. Maintenance and curation of the RDA vocabularies;
 - b. Maintenance and improvement of the extended metadata schema developed by the RDA TIGER project;
 - c. Maintenance and improvement of the guidance materials and supporting templates developed by the project.
 - d. This group should also focus on continued awareness building and limited support for new groups, since the uptake of guidance and tools depends on this awareness.
 - e. The RDA Knowledge Base is currently synchronised with the new RDA website for maintenance of e.g. members, groups, and organisations. This synchronisation will require technical support (addressed as part of the technical sustainability aspect), but will also require oversight - likely provided by this group.

6. The RDA Secretariat will also need to address maintenance and improvement of the following:
 - a. Policies and procedures in respect of publication of RDA outputs and supporting materials;
 - b. Maintaining a contractual relationship with the future hosting and support institution(s) for the RDA Knowledge Base.
7. RDA should augment its reporting of impact via DataCite citation indices, as well as Zenodo download statistics.
8. Since the RDA outputs have an impact that extends beyond the RDA community, it may be argued that costs of the continued operations and maintenance should be (partially) covered by the existing mechanisms of R&I support and science diplomacy, while at the same time ensuring that the governance remains within the RDA community.

4.3 Remaining Challenges and Future Work

1. At the present time, the RDA-KB content is only accessible via the user interface, or by requesting a copy of the data. It is not clear what the preference of the community is in respect of accessing the data - as a reference manager export, as a SPARQL-queryable endpoint, etc. These preferences need to be determined, and a solution implemented.
2. Future work could include the automated retrieval of impact metrics, for example download and view statistics from Zenodo, and [citation metrics from DataCite](#) and [Scholix](#).
3. Work has started on accommodating ad-hoc classifications and vocabularies defined by working groups have started late in the project lifetime, but will require further refinement to operationalise fully.
4. Work has also started on supporting mechanisms of bulk annotation, involving uploads and vocabulary creation for GitHub issue lists, Zotero reference exports, and spreadsheet-based input. This work will have to be completed and operationalised after completion of the RDA TIGER project.
5. In respect of guidance should groups consider publication of their work as a formal specification, the advisory obtained from the expert group is useful, but should ideally be extended to cover procedural aspects of publication as W3C or ISO standards. W3C standards are especially relevant in the context of RDA.
6. EOSC-related links and associations will require future periodic updates that will have to be included into the tasks of maintenance and support personnel. It is not clear who will have this responsibility.
7. While a minimum sustainability plan has been put into place to commence at the completion of the RDA TIGER project, additional funding or revenue to substantially extend and refine the capabilities of the system, as well as direct support to end users and RDA groups, is the ideal.
8. The tools and infrastructure created by the project are reusable in many other contexts (for example by EOSC/ Horizon Europe projects), but there has been very limited opportunity to prepare a value proposition for these end user communities or to engage with them - this remains an underutilised and future exploitation opportunity.

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Annex A: New naming scheme since Q2 2024

Table A.1: Overview of naming changes

Old name	New name	Brief description
Maintenance Platform / Maintenance Facility	RDA Knowledge Base	The system as a whole, consisting of the components below. Demo version currently hosted by DANS ⁵⁷
Graph Database / RDA Graph	RDA Graph	The graph database containing information about outputs, authors, groups and their relationships
Deposit Pipeline	RDA Publisher	The common update path of the RDA Graph supporting automatic addition of relationships and sanity checking of entries
The Web Interface	RDA Discovery	Query the RDA Graph, search outputs, and add entries through a web interface
Annotation tool	RDA Annotator	A browser plugin allowing adding entries (through the RDA Publisher) and “tagging them” using RDA vocabularies

Figure A.1: RDA Applications in the RDA Knowledge Base suite, and its relation to e.g. Zenodo⁵⁸

⁵⁷ <https://rda.dansdemo.nl>

⁵⁸ Adopted from the WP4 presentation at the RDA P23, available at: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17752537